

THE STRAIN RATE DEPENDENCE OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES DURING MONOTONIC AND IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical behavior of composite materials is influenced by several parameters like for instance temperature, moisture content and strain rate. One of these, the strain rate, is the subject of this paper.

Recent investigations have shown that the strength of glass fibres increases dramatically with increasing strain rate, while the influence of strain rate on the strength of carbon and aramid fibres is of little significance. So far one has not paid that much attention to the strain rate dependence of fibre reinforced polymer composites.

This paper deals with the investigation of the influence of the resin on the strain rate dependence of the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced plastics. Tensile and impact tests were carried out on carbon reinforced plastics. The carbon reinforced polymer composites were tensile tested at strain rates from 0,0004 1/s to 100 1/s. The impact speed varied from 1 m/s to 20 m/s. At low to medium strain rates these composites showed an increasing brittleness with strain rate. This was very remarkable for the toughened epoxy, maybe because of a failing toughening mechanism at these strain rates. At high to very high strain rates the composite matrix became more ductile with increasing strain rate. An explanation for this can be the almost adiabatic warming up of the matrix near the crack tip due to the release of plastic deformation energy.

KEYWORDS: Strain rate; Tensile; Low Velocity Impact; Fibre, Graphite; Matrix, Epoxy, Polyetherimide.

1. INTRODUCTION

The high strain rate mechanical behavior of fibre reinforced composites has recently become more important due to the increased use of composite materials which undergo this type of loading. For instance when introducing shock absorbing zones made of composites in

vehicles, the designer needs to know the strain rate dependence of the mechanical properties. Until now few research has been done concerning this strain rate dependence.

The transverse properties of a unidirectional laminate are highly dependent on strain rate. Daniël [1] found for a carbon reinforced epoxy that the E-modulus more then doubled when increasing the strain rate from 10^{-6} 1/s up to 150 1/s. The strength increased almost with 200 %. Research of the same author [2] on an other carbon reinforced epoxy showed an increase of 15 % of the E-modulus and the strength and a decrease of 10 % of the failure strain when increasing the strain rate from 10^{-6} 1/s up to 5 1/s. Myano [3] found only a slight increase of the strength for a strain rate of 0.5 1/s.

The properties of a $[45/-45]_{2s}$ laminate are also very dependent on the strain rate. Harding [4] tested a glass reinforced epoxy and found a strong increase of the strength, failure strain and E-modulus with strain rate (upto 1120 1/s). Al-Salehi [5] found for a glass reinforced epoxy with strain rates to 150 1/s a slighter increase of the strength and the failure strain, while the E-modulus stayed constant. Daniël [2] tested a carbon reinforced epoxy with strain rates ranging from 10^{-6} 1/s to 5 1/s and found an increase of 25 % of the strength and the E-modulus while the failure strain stayed constant.

The strain rate dependence of the longitudinal properties of a unidirectional laminate is influenced by the type of fibre. The results of Harding and Welsh [4,6], Daniël [2] and Myano [3] show that the mechanical properties of carbon reinforced epoxy are almost independent of strain rate. On the other hand, the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced epoxy change a lot with strain rate. Harding and Welsh [4] found a strong increase with strain rate of the strength, the failure strain and the E-modulus. The more recent results with low fibre volume fraction specimens of Harding and Welsh [6] showed on the contrary a decrease of the strength and the failure strain for strain rates higher than 10 1/s due to the pull out of the glass fibres.

In this paper, we will look at the strain rate dependence of carbon reinforced composites made with a toughened epoxy or a thermoplastic (PEI) matrix. In a future publication, we will also report the strain rate dependency of the mechanical behavior of two new composites, namely Arall, a composite made of aluminium and aramid fibres, and Glare, a composite made of aluminium and glass fibres. Their behavior has also been compared with a few types of aluminium alloys.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The research consisted of tensile tests and impact tests carried out on different composite materials. The static tensile tests were done on an MTS tensile testing machine at the faculty of Aeronautical and Aerospace Engineering at the T.U.Delft and on an INSTRON 6025 at the Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering at the K.U.Leuven. The high strain rate impact and tensile tests were done on a Schenck high strain rate testing machine at the

Research Center of the AKZO Co. in Arnhem. The impact speed varied from 1 m/s to 20 m/s and the maximum strain rate for the tensile tests was about 50 up to 100 1/s depending on the stiffness of the specimen. The strain was measured by means of strain gauges and registered with an oscilloscope as a function of time.

Two different carbon reinforced plastic composites were tensile tested. The first composite was made of the toughened epoxy 6376 (Ciba-Geigy) and the carbon fibre T-400 with a fibre volume fraction of 63 %. The second composite was made of the thermoplastic material polyetherimide and the carbon fibre T-330 with a fibre volume fraction of 53 %. The tensile test specimens had the following lay-up: $[90]_8$, $[0_2,90_2]_s$, $[+45/-45]_{2s}$. These two materials were also impact tested (full penetration impact test); the laminate had a cross-ply lay-up: $[0_2,90_2]_{2s}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Carbon reinforced composites

3.1.1. Tensile testing

$[0_2,90_2]_{2s}$

The mechanical properties of the cross-ply do not change with strain rate in a significant way. This is the case for both types of carbon reinforced composites.

$[90]_8$

The transverse properties of the unidirectional laminates are dependent on strain rate. For the laminate with the thermoplastic resin PEI the strength and the failure strain increase with strain rate (see figure 1,2). The E-modulus reaches a maximum at a certain strain rate (see figure 3).

Figure 1. The transverse tensile strength.

The failure strain and the strength of the laminate with the toughened epoxy first slightly decrease and then also increase with strain rate (see figure 1,2). Also the E-modulus reaches a maximum (see figure 3). For both resins the tensile curve is almost linear up to failure.

Figure 2. The transverse failure strain.

Figure 3. The transverse stiffness.

A possible explanation for the initial decrease of the failure strain of the laminate with the toughened epoxy is the embrittlement of the resin with increasing strain rate. Due to the increased strain rate the toughening mechanism has less time to accomplish its task. The increase of the failure strain for PEI and the toughened epoxy in the region of the higher strain rates is possibly due to the warming up of the resin at the crack tip during the crack propagation. A temperature increase at the crack tip locally toughens the resin and decreases the crack growth rate. A simplified calculation learns that a temperature increase of 50 K and more is possible at the crack tip.

The observed change of the fracture surface with strain rate of both laminates supports this explanation. The fracture surface of the PEI laminate shows a lot more deformation of the resin at the highest strain rate, in the form of bigger resin dimples compared to the low strain rate fracture surfaces. The fracture surface of the toughened epoxy laminate tested at the lowest strain rate, shows 50 % of the crack surface running along the fibre-matrix interface. At the highest strain rate, cracks run only through the resin. This change of crack growth path is due to the weakening of the resin at the crack tip. In the mean time the interface strength stays the same, because the carbon fibre guides the dissipated heat easier, so the interface does not warm up.

The increase of the E-modulus with strain rate can be explained by the viscoelastic behavior of the resin. The decrease of the E-modulus at the highest strain rates could be explained in terms of heat dissipation during deformation. Already at low strain levels certain places in the resin will deform more due to the existence of stress concentrations around the fibres. If the yield stress is reached a certain amount of the plastic deformation energy can be released as heat. This heat cannot be dissipated quickly enough at high strain rates, so that the E-modulus decreases with strain rate. The maximum for the E-modulus is reached at lower strain rates for the PEI-laminate due to the higher stress concentrations. The stress concentrations are proportional to the ratio of the transverse modulus of the carbon fibre and the E-modulus of the resin. The E-modulus of PEI is 3 GPa and of the toughened epoxy 3.6 GPa. The transverse modulus of the carbon fibre T-330 is also slightly higher than the transverse modulus of the carbon fibre T-400 because of the less longitudinal oriented structure of the carbon fibre T-330. This makes that the stress concentrations are higher in the laminate which combines the carbon fibre T-330 and the resin PEI than in the laminate with the carbon fibre T-400 and the toughened epoxy.

[+45,-45]_{2s}

The properties of this type of laminate are strongly dependent on strain rate (see figure 4). The

Figure 4. Strain at maximum stress of [+45,-45]_{2s}.

strain at maximum stress of the PEI-laminate decreases a little with strain rate. On the contrary, the strain at maximum stress of the toughened epoxy laminate decreases dramatically with strain rate. This decrease is the result of the embrittlement of the resin. This is also visible on the fracture surface. At low strain rates the resin fails in most cases in a shear like mode. At the higher strain rates the resin fails in a brittle way. The increase of the E-modulus and the yield strength with increasing strain rates can be explained on the basis of the viscoelastic behavior of the resin (see figure 5,6).

Figure 5. E-modulus of [+45,-45]_{2S}.

Figure 6. Tensile strength of [+45,-45]_{2S}.

In this type of laminate no heat dissipation seems to occur or maybe the influence is too little to be visible.

3.1.2. Impact testing

The shape of the impact curve (full penetration) almost does not change with impact speed for

both laminates (PEI and the toughened epoxy). The laminate fails when the 0°-layers break. Also the stiffness of the laminate is mostly influenced by the 0°-layers. Because the 0°-layers show no strain rate dependence, the impact curve will neither show any strain rate dependence.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The tests showed that mainly the resin is responsible for the strain rate dependence of carbon reinforced plastics. The influence of strain rate can be explained by means of two mechanisms.

At low strain rates an increase of strain rate will cause an embrittlement of the resin. This is very striking for the toughened epoxy, may be because of a failing toughening mechanism at higher strain rates.

At high strain rates a warming up of the resin at the crack tip and in zones with a lot of plastic deformation can increase the ductility of the resin.

Depending on the strain rate one of these mechanisms will preponderate.

5. REFERENCES

1. I.M. DANIEL and W.G. HAMILTON, Composite Materials: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 787, 393 (1982).
2. I.M. DANIEL, et. al., Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology, 110, 169 (1988).
3. Y. MYANO, et. al., 30 th National SAMPE Symposium, 257 (1985).
4. J. HARDING and L.M. WELSH, Journal of Materials Science, 18, 1810 (1983).
5. F.A.R. AL-SALEHI, et. al., Journal of Composite Materials, 23, 288 (1989).
6. L.M. WELSH and J. HARDING, ICCM-V, 1517 (1985).

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the ERASMUS-program of the European Communities for supporting L.Lammerant during his stay at T.U.Delft, and M.Bosma of the AKZO Co. for using the high strain rate equipment.

